

Innovative Language Learning Research With Virtual Reality Pedagogical System

Source: [shutterstock.com/metamorworks](https://www.shutterstock.com/metamorworks)

Author: Sayed Hadi Sadeghi is an international author published by Routledge and Springer, Head of Education and Artificial Intelligence Department and Assistant Professor of Cognitive Science and E-learning at the Supreme National Defense University, Iran and Research Assistant at the University of Sydney, Australia. The views contained in this article are the author's alone.

Abstract: Innovation in analysing different methods and techniques promises new avenues for effective education. Learning and teaching processes are becoming increasingly significant for both theoretical and practical reasons. New technologies, such as virtual reality (VR), have been employed in recent years to transform teaching methods and enhance learning. Concurrently, educational psychologists strive to better understand both traditional and electronic learning systems through various techniques. This project focuses on studying brain signals using systems like EEG (electroencephalography) and fNIRS (functional near-infrared spectroscopy) while students engage in different types of learning activities. Specifically, this project adapts EEG for use with an innovative VR language learning system termed Intelligent Pedagogy (INTELLIPED). A series of experimental studies were conducted, collecting behavioural and EEG data to investigate the efficacy of VR in second language learning in two ways: using VR alone and using VR in an 'alert state.' To facilitate this research, an innovative INTELLIPED Virtual Teacher (I-VT) was developed. INTELLIPED, though only pilot-tested with confidential results, can

be designed for specific applications. It represents a major advancement in educational technology, offering personalised learning through artificial intelligence (AI) and VR. Its versatile uses in civil and military contexts have the potential to transform language and skill learning.

Bottom-line-up-front: This essay highlights how advanced technologies like VR, EEG and ERPs (Event-related potentials) can inspire effective language learning and education. By integrating these tools, educators can create personalised, immersive learning experiences that enhance engagement and improve outcomes, addressing the limitations of traditional methods.

Problem statement: How can virtual reality hypnosis (VRH) amend the shortcomings of conventional hypnosis, which is impractical in educational settings due to its need for expert intervention and inducing a drowsy state?

So what?: INTELLIPED Virtual Teacher (I-VT) employs EEG and fNIRS to monitor brain activity, adapting learning experiences in real-time to optimise the learning process, maintain optimal conditions and reduce cognitive overload. It aims to develop a learning framework, an alert hypnosis programme and ERP-based algorithms, ultimately enhancing language learning strategies and tools.

Shifting Teaching Approaches

Education has predominantly been teacher-centred in the past few decades, with one teacher sometimes instructing 20 to 40 students in a classroom. This traditional approach focuses on predetermined subjects for all students.[1] However, since the early 21st century, there has been a significant shift in general approaches to education.[2] Contemporary teaching methodologies now need to become more flexible to address students' diverse interests and needs.[3]

Modern technologies offer various capabilities that can support this transition, potentially serving as valuable tools in today's evolving educational setting. As time progresses, technology increasingly dominates the educational landscape. Educators widely acknowledge that using technology often leads to significant learning gains and benefits.[4] Modern technological tools significantly enhance learning by providing interactive, personalised and flexible educational experiences. E-learning, social media and computer-based tools aid in adaptive teaching and meta-cognitive regulation, helping students manage

their learning processes and individual paces and styles,[5], [6], [7], [8] while simulation tools and game-like materials blend traditional and digital resources to make learning comprehensive and enjoyable.[9] Mobile device-based systems support inquiry-based learning, improving student achievement and encouraging positive perceptions of learning tools.[10] Digital tools in math and science enhance outcomes through interactive experiences.[11] Web-based tools extend learning beyond the classroom, catering to diverse learning styles and boosting motivation.[12], [13] Furthermore, frameworks and cognitive tools enhance teachers' pedagogical knowledge, leading to better teaching strategies and improved student outcomes.[14], [15] Some researchers even suggest that interaction with technology can affect brain structure and function.[16] Therefore, this aspect of technology can be an invaluable instrument, creating a different pathway for educational enhancement.

Utilising Immersive Virtual Reality in Education

Technological advances such as computers, tablets and smartphones have already demonstrated significant benefits in education. Now, a new technology gaining mainstream attention is virtual reality (VR).[17] Virtual reality is a human-computer interface that immerses users in an environment, primarily using auditory and visual feedback but also incorporating other sensory inputs.[18] Previous studies have shown that VR provides a rich and powerful environment for educational purposes.[19], [20] Through its potential, humankind can create three-dimensional (3D) environments for learners, allowing learners to experience simulated real-life settings and interact more effectively with educational materials. Hu-Au and Lee (2017) highlighted several issues in traditional pedagogy and explored how VR can offer opportunities to enhance educational systems.[21]

Research indicates that student engagement in academic activities is crucial for both learning and personal development.[22] However, low student engagement remains a significant challenge in traditional education. This lack of engagement is a primary contributor to various negative outcomes, including dissatisfaction, adverse experiences and higher dropout rates.[23], [24]

Virtual reality possesses unique characteristics that significantly enhance student engagement.[25] Some VR programmes enable teachers to take their students on virtual and computer-generated field trips to simulated locations as diverse as Mars and the ocean floor. This capability can spark a new interest in the subject matter and improve personal engagement.[26] Additionally, the literature

highlights that virtual reality improves engagement through a strong sense of presence and immersion.[27] This heightened sense of presence is one of the key ways VR boosts educational engagement.[28]

Another issue with classroom-based learning is the absence of 'situated' learning. Students frequently encounter concepts and terms without understanding their broader applicability.[29], [30] This lack of authentic experience leads to ineffective and fragmented learning. In contrast, virtual reality can address this problem by offering environments where students can engage in realistic experiences. VR allows students to have genuine and immersive interactions with various materials, thereby improving their learning outcomes.[31]

Hew and Cheung (2010) conducted a systematic review of the use of three-dimensional (3D) immersive virtual worlds in educational settings.[32] They identified three primary applications for virtual worlds: (1) communication spaces, (2) spatial simulations, and (3) experiential spaces ('acting' on the world), where users can interact with the environment. Additionally, their research indicated that virtual worlds could enhance various factors related to learning outcomes. Incorporating virtual reality into classroom instruction or distance learning, therefore, offers significant advantages for educational systems.

Learning in Alert State

Researchers continuously strive to discover efficient techniques for enhancing students' educational performance. For nearly a century, numerous studies have investigated the relationship between learning and alert states. Most research initiatives have focused on either studying while in a trance state or employing trance induction, deepening, and a series of posthypnotic suggestions to improve concentration, increase motivation, reduce test anxiety and enhance study habits.[33], [34], [35], [36], [37], [38], [39] Studies indicate that an alert state can enhance both simple learning performance and higher-level cognitive processes.[40] Consequently, an alert state has long been considered a valuable educational tool.[41]

However, there are numerous limitations to using the alert state for educational purposes. Oetting (1964) highlighted some of these challenges and proposed a new type of hypnosis that would be more suitable for educational settings.[42] Traditional hypnosis techniques for trance induction and

deepening have been developed within clinical contexts and do not meet the requirements of an educational environment. As Oetting (1964) explained: *“Trance induction through the usual methods leave the subject in a relaxed, sleepy state that is unsuitable for active and intense study. If the subject is to study in the trance state itself, some directions leading to a state of greater awareness are necessary ... This contradiction may in itself lead to confusion and disturbance on the part of the subject that will interfere rather than assist with the study process.”*[43]

Another problem is the authoritative nature of the alert state, which restricts its application to the presence of a therapist. Oetting (1964) noted that *“the reliability of posthypnotic suggestion is not good, particularly when suggestions come into conflict with already established patterns of behaviour”*. [44]

Oetting (1964) proposed as solution an auto-hypnotic ‘alert trance’ for pedagogical purposes.[45] Unlike traditional hypnosis, his novel method of induction did not involve eye closure or drowsiness; instead, it employed suggestions to sharpen the student’s attention. Oetting’s work was an early exploration of using a new type of hypnosis for academic problem-solving systems. Subsequent research has demonstrated the potential of ‘alert trance’ and its applicability in educational settings.[46], [47], [48] A literature review conducted on the effects of both traditional and alert state hypnosis on education concluded that hypnosis in any form could enhance memory and the learning process.[49]

Alert Hypnosis by Virtual Reality

In conventional hypnosis, an expert is required as a medium to guide a subject into a trance state. However, finding well-trained experts in this modality can be challenging, creating a barrier to the use of hypnosis in certain situations.[50] As a result, researchers continuously seek reliable methods to expand the application of hypnosis. Recently, some scholars have explored the use of computer technology to create hypnosis programmes. Patterson et al. (2006) conducted the first study using computerised hypnosis by employing immersive VR as a new medium.[51] Their goal *“with virtual reality hypnosis was to develop a three dimensional, immersive VR technology that could guide the patient through the same steps that are used when hypnosis is induced through an interpersonal process”* [52].

The early studies on Virtual Reality Hypnosis (VRH) aimed to explore its potential for delivering hypnotic analgesia.[53], [54], [55], [56] Previous research indicated that hypnosis has analgesic effects and can be

used as a method for pain reduction.[57] However, the necessity of a clinical expert to perform hypnosis limits its widespread application. Patterson et al. (2010) conducted a randomised, controlled study to test whether hypnosis could be integrated with VR technology in managing injury pain. They used two control groups (and another under VRH) to distinguish the effects of hypnosis with and without virtual reality environment. The first control group received VR distraction (VRD) without hypnosis, while the second control group received standard treatment without either VR or hypnosis. The results showed significant differences in pain reduction between the VRH-treated and control groups, suggesting that it is possible to create a VR programme that guides individuals into a hypnotic state without requiring the real presence of a medium.[58]

Alert Hypnosis and Second Language Learning

Early research on VRH primarily focused on pain reduction. However, VRH can also be applied to language learning. In an increasingly interconnected global society, learning a second language has become a crucial skill for students. However, mastering a second language is often challenging, thereby necessitating the exploration of methods to enhance students' learning. Second language learning has gained significant attention in recent years from various disciplines, including psychology, education and linguistics.[59] INTELLIPED, as an integrated tool using VR methods, can positively model the cognitive processes involved, particularly in second language learning, enhancing understanding and improving language learning. Numerous researchers have dedicated their efforts to identifying effective strategies for enhancing language learning.[60], [61] Effective strategies for enhancing language learning involve immersive experiences, communicative and task-based approaches, multimodal learning, technology integration, constructive feedback and cultural exposure. Some studies suggest that hypnosis could potentially enhance language learning.[62] Therefore, leveraging virtual reality alert hypnosis presents an opportunity to improve the efficacy of second language education.

Incorporating VR and Electroencephalography

VR offers a compelling platform for individuals to immerse themselves in realistic environments. However, recent advancements in VR technology have transformed it from a mere experience into a

tool for deeper exploration. Researchers have begun investigating brain activity during VR experiences by integrating electroencephalography (EEG) sensors with VR technology.[63], [64], [65], [66] EEG is an electrophysiological monitoring method used to record the brain's electrical activity. Event-related potentials (ERPs), a type of EEG, enable recording brain activities associated with various cognitive functions.[67] Thus, the combination of VR and EEG provides a novel tool for investigating changes in the brain resulting from mental activities. Some of the applications of ERPs which can be exploited in enhancing second language learning include:

- **Monitoring attentional processes:** Attention has been defined as the mechanism through which we select stimuli from the vast amount of information available through our senses, stored memories and other cognitive processes.[68] Research on attention has revealed that ERP components reliably reflect the differential processing of attended and unattended information.[69], [70] *"By recording ERPs to attended and unattended stimuli, direct evidence can be obtained about the level of processing attained by these stimuli"*.[71] Thus, ERP signals may serve as indicators to determine the current attentional state of learners and to distinguish between attended and unattended materials.
- **Alleviating mental fatigue:** Mental fatigue, a psychobiological state arising from prolonged periods of demanding cognitive activity, has attracted significant attention in research.[72], [73], [74] This state has been found to impair various cognitive and behavioural functions, such as attentional focus and planning.[75] Therefore, reducing mental fatigue could enhance learning processes. Previous studies have delved into the ERP correlates of mental fatigue[76], [77], suggesting that mental fatigue caused by different kinds of cognitive activity can be characterised by changes in the ERP components.
- **Monitoring language level:** Language learning is a cognitive process that leaves discernable traces in brain signals. ERPs have proven effective in distinguishing between second language learners and native speakers.[78], [79] Moreover, studies have demonstrated that ERPs can reveal nuanced differences among second language learners at various proficiency levels, differences that may be challenging to detect or may go unnoticed with conventional behavioural measures.[80], [81] These findings span a range of language processes, encompassing lexical, syntactic, morphosyntactic and semantic aspects.[82], [83], [84], [85] Consequently, brain signals offer a potent means of determining language proficiency and improving the progress of second language learners.

This innovative language learning research with virtual reality, termed Intelligent Pedagogy (INTELLIPED), aims to develop a robust tool for language learning and other applicable educational materials. It functions as a dynamic system employing ERP algorithms to assess individuals' language proficiency by analysing diverse mental states. The INTELLIPED Virtual Teacher (I-VT) initiates the learning process instantly by identifying an appropriate mental state and continuously monitoring brain activity throughout the course, thereby ensuring prevention of experiencing materials during incompatible mental states. Any indications of fatigue or cognitive overload prompt the I-VT to implement pre-planned interventions. Furthermore, the I-VT comprehensively monitors the learning session and evaluates the learning of materials based on individuals' brain responses.

Second Language – Intelligent Learning

The motivation behind this research project lies in conducting research that draws on insights from psychology, neuroscience, and computer science to bolster second language learning. This endeavour employs the innovative I-VT system, in which EEG data are collected while students engage with it. Subsequently, the data are fed back into the system to direct and optimise the learning process.

This project encompasses four primary phases. Firstly, developing a framework for a language learning system akin to neural networks, which is detailed in the Method and Design section. Secondly, the focus shifts to developing an alert hypnosis programme tailored for the I-VT system, followed by conducting initial usability studies. The third phase involves acquiring ERP signals associated with learning levels and mental states. Finally, in the fourth phase, algorithms are devised to utilise ERPs automatically. The ultimate version translates brain signals into instructional commands, facilitating and directing language learning.

Method and Design

This project creates an intelligent method for second language learning, using artificial intelligence to autonomously manage the learning process without external intervention, including from a real teacher

or a learner. All aspects of learning are controlled by the individual's brain functions through pre-defined algorithms. Achieving this goal requires expertise in both technology and psychology:

- A virtual teacher guides the overall learning course by analysing brain signals to execute alert states and lead the learning process. This teacher runs all modules, which are designed based on academic research and data collection on alert state instructions, encompassing all language skills.[86], [87], [88], [89]
- The final programme mirrors the structure of neural networks, consisting of three major components: units, modules and cells. The largest component, the unit, is arranged hierarchically according to linguistic levels. Units are subdivided into several modules, each encompassing specific activities designed for educational sessions. Each module, in turn, contains numerous cells transmitting particular language materials. These materials include all the information necessary for effective communication. The project's structure is dynamically organised, with the nature of the modules defined by the specific cells and their interrelationships. Language cells are not confined to a single module and may appear in multiple modules. Consequently, the relationships among the cells determine the modules' characteristics. This innovative system offers two significant advantages. First, it enables the measurement of ERP signals associated with each cell or module. Second, it allows for sufficient repetition of linguistic material to facilitate learning. By measuring ERP signals during subsequent exposure to a cell, the programme can assess the amount of learning for that specific cell or module.
- Algorithms are designed to utilise ERP patterns for managing learning sessions. The virtual teacher, developed in the first step, uses these outputs to manage the course.[90]
- The project identifies various EEG/ERP signals related to mental states such as attention, mental fatigue and language proficiency. Deep learning is employed as a tool to analyse these signals and discover intricate structures in large datasets,[91] utilising neural networks with multiple layers to model complex data patterns. The models of deep learning—a subset of machine learning within artificial intelligence (AI)—are constructed based on artificial neural networks inspired by the human brain's structure and function.

Potential Risks and Safety Measures

The INTELLIPED system integrates VR and neurotechnology to advance education but must address significant security risks. To safeguard data against potential threats, it categorises and stores raw data in a secure warehouse with three distinct security levels. This process begins with the generation of data, followed by assigning data to appropriate pools, and finally, integrating the data with professional oversight. This multipronged approach aims to compartmentalise data handling and minimise exposure to risks at each stage.

A critical measure to ensure the secure processing and analysis of data related to the INTELLIPED system involves storing and managing data in isolated environments. The risk of cyberattacks necessitates robust cybersecurity measures to safeguard data integrity. Unauthorised access to sensitive data could lead to significant privacy violations and undermine the credibility of the research and system. This isolation is essential to protect against cyberattacks and related risks, ensuring that data processing occurs in environments devoid of web connectivity. By keeping EEG and ERP signals, as well as the VR components, offline, the system avoids noise and erratic resonances that could disrupt experiments and compromise learning outcomes.

Web connectivity and similar digital interactions pose several risks, including the potential for bioresonance interference and machine biases, particularly those stemming from the VR teaching system I-VT. These biases can lead to errors in experimental results and adversely affect learning outcomes. Additionally, there are concerns about the potential harm to individuals, such as memory loss or cognitive impairments, if data security is breached or if the system malfunctions.

Ethical considerations are also paramount in developing and deploying the INTELLIPED system. Ensuring ethical approval and compliance with stringent ethical standards is necessary to protect the rights and well-being of learners/participants. Future updates to ethical approval checklists are recommended to address any emerging issues and to maintain the integrity of the process.

While the INTELLIPED system offers substantial potential for enhancing educational methodologies through advanced VR and neurotechnological integration, it is imperative to address the associated risks comprehensively. By implementing stringent data management protocols, ensuring isolated data processing environments and adhering to ethical standards, the system can mitigate security threats and enhance the reliability and effectiveness of its educational outcomes. A step-by-step, case-by-case approach ensures that each individual's data is handled with the utmost care, safeguarding both the integrity of the research and the well-being of its participants/learners.

Significance, Applications and Conclusion

Technology has demonstrated how following the correct pathways can improve the learning process and comprehensive cognitive behaviour.[92] The significance of INTELLIPED lies in its ability to use technology to enhance learning processes and comprehensive cognitive behaviour. By creating virtual curricula based on new teaching and learning concepts through personalised learning methods, INTELLIPED places learners in the optimal cognitive state to enhance their acquisition of knowledge. Integrating meta-cognitive approaches, INTELLIPED promises to bring about positive changes in educational technology, addressing both current and future educational gaps and raising the expectations of educational systems. What sets INTELLIPED apart is its design pattern for a meta-cognitive framework within a virtual hypnotic pedagogical system. This framework is a coherent, strategic implementation that utilises advanced VR and hypnosis techniques to create personalised, immersive learning experiences. For example, the system uses real-time data analytics and deep learning algorithms to adapt the curriculum dynamically to the learner's progress, ensuring that each learner remains engaged and challenged at an appropriate level. By coupling these advanced technologies with a thorough understanding of cognitive science, INTELLIPED offers concrete solutions to enhance educational outcomes. This project paves the way for significant advancements in how knowledge is imparted and learned, providing a robust, scalable model for future educational technologies.

The main target audiences for the INTELLIPED project fall into two primary sectors: civil contexts and military/security-providing institutes. In industrial and semi-industrial environments, INTELLIPED is designed to enhance human resources and workforce efficiency by improving familiarity with and the ability to learn new languages, which is critical for enhancing communication and productivity. In sports infrastructure, INTELLIPED can also be used to analyse upcoming matches in significant tournaments and facilitate communication among multinational training staff, ensuring seamless coordination and strategic planning. Additionally, INTELLIPED's ultra-human, AI- and VR-based learning methodologies can transform academic education, fostering an efficient mentor-to-mentor, which is a human-machine learning process.

For military and security-providing institutes, INTELLIPED plays a vital role in educating highly efficient members during the recruitment process by training them in a second language of choice or need. This is essential for international communication and operational effectiveness. While some organisations prioritise national identity and language, INTELLIPED facilitates second language learning to bolster security against threats like espionage and infiltration. Its deep learning methods with rapidly functioning capabilities ensure that security personnel can quickly adapt to high-tech learning environments, keeping pace with the growing field of security technology. Defence and security sectors can benefit from INTELLIPED by transforming their learning and cognitive science approaches, aligning them with the latest advancements in educational technology and cognitive research.

Although the instances of using INTELLIPED are limited and have been utilised on a pilot basis, the information and results cannot be divulged due to confidentiality and ethical concerns, and it has been designed and targeted for particular applications in mind. The INTELLIPED project represents a significant leap forward in educational technology, providing personalised, meta-cognitive learning experiences through advanced AI and VR. Its applications in both civil and military contexts demonstrate its versatility and potential to inspire novel ways of how languages and other skills are taught and learned, ultimately enhancing communication, efficiency and security in various sectors.

Endnotes

- [1] Rachel Bolstad, and Jane Gilbert. *Disciplining and drafting or 21st century learning?: Rethinking the New Zealand senior secondary curriculum for the future*, Wellington: NZCER Press, 2008.
- [2] Guy Claxton, and Margaret Carr, "A framework for teaching learning: the dynamics of disposition," *Early years* 24, no. 1 (2004): 87-97.
- [3] Wendy Fox-Turnbull, "Teaching and Learning in Technology: Section Introduction," In *Handbook of Technology Education*, edited by Marc J. de Vries, 1-9, Springer International Handbooks of Education. Cham: Springer, 2017.
- [4] Neil Selwyn, *Education and Technology: Key Issues and Debates*, Bloomsbury Publishing, 2016.
- [5] David A. Cook, "Teaching with Technological Tools," in *An Introduction to Medical Teaching*, eds. Kathryn N. Huggett, and William B. Jeffries (Dordrecht: Springer, 2014), 123–146.
- [6] Roger Azevedo, "Computer Environments as Metacognitive Tools for Enhancing Learning," *Educational Psychologist* 40, no. 4 (2005): 193–97.
- [7] M. U. Bokhari, Sadaf Ahmad, Shadab Alam, and Faheem Masoodi, "Modern tools and technologies for interactive learning," *Environment* 13, no. 15 (2011): 17-18.
- [8] Elizabeth A. Cudney and Julie Ezzell, "A Systematic Review of Technological Advancements to Enhance Learning," in *Proceedings of the 2015 ASEE Annual Conference and Exposition*, Seattle, WA, June 2015 (Washington, DC: American Society for Engineering Education, 2015).

- [9] Miika Lehtonen, "Simulations as Mental Tools for Network-Based Group Learning." In *E-Training Practices for Professional Organizations: IFIP TC3/WG3.3 Fifth Working Conference on eTRAIN Practices for Professional Organizations (eTrain 2003) July 7–11, 2003, Pori, Finland*, 11-17. New York: Springer US, 2005.
- [10] Krittawaya Thongkoo, Kannika Daungcharone, and Patcharin Panjaburee, "A Development of Ubiquitous Learning Support System Based on an Enhanced Inquiry-Based Learning Approach," *International Journal of Mobile Learning and Organisation* 13, no. 2 (2019): 129–151.
- [11] Delia Hillmayr, Lisa Ziernwald, Frank Reinhold, Sarah I. Hofer, and Kristina M. Reiss, "The potential of digital tools to enhance mathematics and science learning in secondary schools: A context-specific meta-analysis," *Computers & Education* 153 (2020): 103897.
- [12] Nafiseh Zarei, Supyan Hussin, and Taufik Rashid, "Overcoming Learning Time and Space Constraints through Technological Tool," *Advances in Language and Literary Studies* 6, no. 4 (2015): 151-157.
- [13] Dumitru Dan Burdescu, "E-Learning Tools for a Software Platform," in *Smart Education and Smart e-Learning*, eds. Vladimir L. Uskov, Robert J. Howlett, and Lakhmi C. Jain, Smart Innovation, Systems and Technologies, vol. 41 (Cham: Springer, 2015), 231–241.
- [14] Alister Jones and Judy Moreland, "Enhancing practicing primary school teachers' pedagogical content knowledge in technology." *International Journal of Technology and Design Education* 14 (2004): 121-140.
- [15] Tim Bristol and L. Jane Rosati. "Successful concept-based learning through the integration of technology." *Teaching and Learning in Nursing* 8 (2013): 112-116.
- [16] Marc Prensky, "Digital Natives, Digital Immigrants," *On the Horizon* 9, no. 5 (2001): 1–6.
- [17] Elliot Hu-Au, and Joey J. Lee. "Virtual reality in education: a tool for learning in the experience age," *International Journal of Innovation in Education* 4, no. 4 (2017): 215-226.
- [18] David D. Luxton, "An Introduction to Artificial Intelligence in Behavioral and Mental Health Care," In *Artificial Intelligence in Behavioral and Mental Health Care*, 1-26, Academic Press, 2016.
- [19] Laura Freina, and Michela Ott, "A Literature Review on Immersive Virtual Reality in Education: State of the Art and Perspectives," In *The International Scientific Conference eLearning and Software for Education*, vol. 1, no. 133, pp. 10-1007. 2015.
- [20] Veronica S. Pantelidis, "Reasons to use virtual reality in education and training courses and a model to determine when to use virtual reality," *Themes in science and technology education* 2 (2009): 59-70.
- [21] Elliot Hu-Au, and Joey J. Lee, "Virtual reality in education: a tool for learning in the experience age" *International Journal of Innovation in Education* 4, no. 4 (2017): 215-226.
- [22] Ömer Delialioğlu, "Student engagement in blended learning environments with lecture-based and problem-based instructional approaches," *Journal of Educational Technology & Society* 15, no. 3 (2012): 310-322.
- [23] Ibid., 310-322.
- [24] Elliot Hu-Au, and Joey J. Lee, "Virtual reality in education: a tool for learning in the experience age" *International Journal of Innovation in Education* 4, no. 4 (2017): 215-226.
- [25] Brenda Eschenbrenner, Fiona Fui-Hoon Nah, and Keng Siau, "3-D virtual worlds in education: Applications, benefits, issues, and opportunities," *Journal of Database Management (JDM)* 19, no. 4 (2008): 91-110.
- [26] Elliot Hu-Au, and Joey J. Lee, "Virtual reality in education: a tool for learning in the experience age," *International Journal of Innovation in Education* 4, no. 4 (2017): 215-226.
- [27] Barney Dalgarno, and Mark JW Lee, "What are the learning affordances of 3-D virtual environments?," *British Journal of Educational Technology* 41, no. 1 (2010): 10-32.
- [28] Elliot Hu-Au, and Joey J. Lee, "Virtual reality in education: a tool for learning in the experience age" *International Journal of Innovation in Education* 4, no. 4 (2017): 215-226.

- [29] James Paul Gee, *Situated Language and Learning: A Critique of Traditional Schooling*, Routledge, 2004.
- [30] Elliot Hu-Au, and Joey J. Lee, "Virtual reality in education: a tool for learning in the experience age" *International Journal of Innovation in Education* 4, no. 4 (2017): 215-226.
- [31] Idem.
- [32] Khe Foon Hew, and Wing Sum Cheung, "Use of three-dimensional (3-D) immersive virtual worlds in K-12 and higher education settings: A review of the research," *British Journal of Educational Technology* 41, no. 1 (2010): 33-55.
- [33] E. R. Oetting, "Hypnosis and concentration in study," *American Journal of Clinical Hypnosis* 7, no. 2 (1964): 148-151.
- [34] Stanley Krippner, "The use of hypnosis with elementary and secondary school children in a summer reading clinic," *American Journal of Clinical Hypnosis* 8, no. 4 (1966): 261-266.
- [35] Stanley Krippner. "The use of hypnosis and the improvement of academic achievement." *The Journal of Special Education* 4, no. 4 (1970): 451-460.
- [36] Vincent G. Eisele, and J. J. Higgins, "Hypnosis in educational and moral problems," *American Journal of Clinical Hypnosis* 4, no. 4 (1962): 259-263.
- [37] Hallack McCord, and Charles I. Sherrill III, "A note on increased ability to do calculus post-hypnotically," *American Journal of Clinical Hypnosis* 4, no. 2 (1961): 124-124.
- [38] A. B. Sears, "Hypnosis and Recall," *International Journal of Clinical and Experimental Hypnosis* 4, no. 4 (1956): 165-171.
- [39] Anthony J. Summo and Fabian L. Rouke, "The use of hypnosis in a college counseling service," *American Journal of Clinical Hypnosis* 8, no. 2 (1965): 114-116.
- [40] David M. Wark, "Traditional and alert hypnosis for education: A literature review," *American Journal of Clinical Hypnosis* 54, no. 2 (2011): 96-106.
- [41] Stanley Krippner, "The use of hypnosis with elementary and secondary school children in a summer reading clinic," *American Journal of Clinical Hypnosis* 8, no. 4 (1966): 451-460.
- [42] E. R. Oetting, "Hypnosis and concentration in study," *American Journal of Clinical Hypnosis* 7, no. 2 (1964): 148-151.
- [43] Ibid., 148.
- [44] Ibid., 149.
- [45] E. R. Oetting, "Hypnosis and concentration in study," *American Journal of Clinical Hypnosis* 7, no. 2 (1964): 148-151.
- [46] Robert M. Liebert, Norma Rubin, and Ernest R. Hilgard, "The effects of suggestions of alertness in hypnosis on paired-associate learning," *Journal of Personality* (1965).
- [47] David M. Wark, "Traditional and alert hypnosis for education: A literature review," *American Journal of Clinical Hypnosis* 54, no. 2 (2011): 277-287.
- [48] H. M. De Vos and DAm Louw, "The effect of hypnotic training programs on the academic performance of students," *American Journal of Clinical Hypnosis* 49, no. 2 (2006): 101-112.
- [49] David M. Wark, "Traditional and alert hypnosis for education: A literature review," *American Journal of Clinical Hypnosis* 54, no. 2 (2011): 96-106.
- [50] Aubriana M. Teeley, Maryam Soltani, Shelley A. Wiechman, Mark P. Jensen, Sam R. Sharar, and David R. Patterson, "Virtual reality hypnosis pain control in the treatment of multiple fractures: a case series," *American Journal of Clinical Hypnosis* 54, no. 3 (2012): 184-194.
- [51] David R. Patterson, Shelley A. Wiechman, Mark Jensen, and Sam R. Sharar, "Hypnosis delivered through immersive virtual reality for burn pain: A clinical case series," *International Journal of Clinical and Experimental Hypnosis* 54, no. 2 (2006): 130-142.
- [52] Ibid., 133.
- [53] Ibid., 130-142.

- [54] Askay, Shelley Wiechman, David R. Patterson, and Sam R. Sharar, "Virtual reality hypnosis," *Contemporary Hypnosis* 26, no. 1 (2009): 40-47.
- [55] Maryam Soltani, Aubriana M. Teeley, Shelley A. Wiechman, Mark P. Jensen, Sam R. Sharar, and David R. Patterson, "Virtual reality hypnosis for pain control in a patient with gluteal hidradenitis: a case report," *Contemporary hypnosis & integrative therapy* 28, no. 2 (2011): 142.
- [56] Aubriana M. Teeley, Maryam Soltani, Shelley A. Wiechman, Mark P. Jensen, Sam R. Sharar, and David R. Patterson, "Virtual reality hypnosis pain control in the treatment of multiple fractures: a case series," *American Journal of Clinical Hypnosis* 54, no. 3 (2012): 184-194.
- [57] David R. Patterson, and Mark P. Jensen. "Hypnosis and clinical pain." *Psychological bulletin* 129, no. 4 (2003): 495.
- [58] David R. Patterson, Mark P. Jensen, Shelley A. Wiechman, and Sam R. Sharar. "Virtual reality hypnosis for pain associated with recovery from physical trauma." *Intl. Journal of Clinical and Experimental Hypnosis* 58, no. 3 (2010): 288-300.
- [59] Janet G. Van Hell and Natasha Tokowicz, "Event-related brain potentials and second language learning: Syntactic processing in late L2 learners at different L2 proficiency levels," *Second Language Research* 26, no. 1 (2010): 43-74.
- [60] J. Michael O'Malley and Anna Uhl Chamot, *Learning Strategies in Second Language Acquisition*, Cambridge University Press, 1990.
- [61] Stella Hurd and Tim Lewis, eds, *Language Learning Strategies in Independent Settings*, Multilingual Matters, 2008.
- [62] Yakup Çetin, O. Arda Çimen, and Zeynep Ebrar Yetkiner, "Using hypnosis to enhance learning second language vocabulary," *American Journal of Clinical Hypnosis* 58, no. 4 (2016): 399-410.
- [63] Jessica D. Bayliss and Dana H. Ballard, "Single trial P3 epoch recognition in a virtual environment," *Neurocomputing* 32 (2000): 637-642.
- [64] Walter F. Bischof and Pierre Boulanger, "Spatial navigation in virtual reality environments: an EEG analysis," *Cyberpsychology & behavior* 6, no. 5 (2003): 487-495.
- [65] Thomas Baumgartner, Lilian Valko, Michaela Esslen, and Lutz Jäncke, "Neural correlate of spatial presence in an arousing and noninteractive virtual reality: an EEG and psychophysiology study," *CyberPsychology & Behavior* 9, no. 1 (2006): 30-45.
- [66] Johanne Tromp, David Peeters, Antje S. Meyer, and Peter Hagoort, "The combined use of virtual reality and EEG to study language processing in naturalistic environments," *Behavior Research Methods* 50 (2018): 862-869.
- [67] Monica Fabiani, Gabriele Gratton, and Michael G. H. Coles, "Event-Related Brain Potentials: Methods, Theory, and Applications," In *Handbook of Psychophysiology*, edited by John T. Cacioppo, Louis G. Tassinary, and Gary G. Berntson, 53-84, New York: Cambridge University Press, 2000.
- [68] Robert J. Sternberg, and Karin Sternberg, *Cognitive Psychology*, Nelson Education, 2016.
- [69] A. A. Wijers, Gysbertus Mulder, Th C. Gunter, and H. G. O. M. Smid, "Brain potential analysis of selective attention," In *Handbook of perception and action*, vol. 3, 333-387, Academic Press, 1996.
- [70] Maarten AS Boksem, Theo F. Meijman, and Monicque M. Lorist, "Effects of mental fatigue on attention: an ERP study," *Cognitive brain research* 25, no. 1 (2005): 107-116.
- [71] Ibid., 108.
- [72] Ibid., 107-116.
- [73] Maarten AS Boksem, and Mattie Tops. "Mental fatigue: costs and benefits." *Brain research reviews* 59, no. 1 (2008): 125-139.
- [74] Masaaki Tanaka, Akira Ishii, and Yasuyoshi Watanabe, "Neural effects of mental fatigue caused by continuous attention load: a magnetoencephalography study," *Brain research* 1561 (2014): 60-66.
- [75] Maarten AS Boksem, and Mattie Tops. "Mental fatigue: costs and benefits." *Brain research reviews* 59, no. 1 (2008): 125-139.

- [76] Maarten AS Boksem, Theo F. Meijman, and Monicque M. Lorist. "Effects of mental fatigue on attention: an ERP study." *Cognitive brain research* 25, no. 1 (2005): 107-116.
- [77] Sungchul Mun, Eun-Soo Kim, and Min-Chul Park, "Effect of mental fatigue caused by mobile 3D viewing on selective attention: An ERP study," *International Journal of Psychophysiology* 94, no. 3 (2014): 373-381.
- [78] Christine M. Weber-Fox and Helen J. Neville, "Maturational constraints on functional specialisations for language processing: ERP and behavioral evidence in bilingual speakers," *Journal of cognitive neuroscience* 8, no. 3 (1996): 231-256.
- [79] Anja Hahne and Angela D. Friederici "Electrophysiological evidence for two steps in syntactic analysis: Early automatic and late controlled processes.," *Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience* 11, no. 2 (1999): 194-205.
- [80] Sonja Rossi, Manfred F. Gugler, Angela D. Friederici, and Anja Hahne, "The impact of proficiency on syntactic second-language processing of German and Italian: Evidence from event-related potentials," *Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience* 18, no. 12 (2006): 2030-2048.
- [81] Janet G. Van Hell and Natasha Tokowicz, "Event-related brain potentials and second language learning: Syntactic processing in late L2 learners at different L2 proficiency levels," *Second Language Research* 26, no. 1 (2010): 43-74.
- [82] Judith McLaughlin, Lee Osterhout, and Albert Kim, "Neural correlates of second-language word learning: Minimal instruction produces rapid change," *Nature Neuroscience* 7, no. 7 (2004): 703-704.
- [83] Yuen Na um, Katherine J. Midgley, Phillip J. Holcomb, and Jonathan Grainger, "An ERP study on initial second language vocabulary learning," *Psychophysiology* 51, no. 4 (2014): 364-373.
- [84] Lee Osterhout, Andrew Poliakov, Kayo Inoue, Judith McLaughlin, Geoffrey Valentine, Ilona Pitkanen, Cheryl Frenck-Mestre, and Julia Hirschensohn, "Second-language learning and changes in the brain," *Journal of Neurolinguistics* 21, no. 6 (2008): 509-521.
- [85] Janet G. Van Hell and Natasha Tokowicz, "Event-related brain potentials and second language learning: Syntactic processing in late L2 learners at different L2 proficiency levels," *Second Language Research* 26, no. 1 (2010): 43-74.
- [86] David R. Patterson, Shelley A. Wiechman, Mark Jensen, and Sam R. Sharar, "Hypnosis delivered through immersive virtual reality for burn pain: A clinical case series," *International Journal of Clinical and Experimental Hypnosis* 54, no. 2 (2006): 130-142.
- [87] Patterson, David R., Mark P. Jensen, Shelley A. Wiechman, and Sam R. Sharar. "Virtual reality hypnosis for pain associated with recovery from physical trauma." *Intl. Journal of Clinical and Experimental Hypnosis* 58, no. 3 (2010): 288-300.
- [88] Michael D. Yapko, *Essentials of hypnosis*, Routledge, 2015.
- [89] Michael R. Nash and Amanda J. Barnier, eds. *The Oxford Handbook of Hypnosis: Theory, Research, and Practice*, Oxford University Press, 2012.
- [90] David White, Joseph Ciorciari, Colin Carbis, and David Liley, "EEG correlates of virtual reality hypnosis," *International Journal of Clinical and Experimental Hypnosis* 57, no. 1 (2008): 94-116.
- [91] Yann LeCun, Yoshua Bengio, and Geoffrey Hinton, "Deep learning," *Nature* 521, no. 7553 (2015): 436-444.
- [92] Sayed Hadi Sadeghi, *E-learning Practice in Higher Education: A Mixed-Method Comparative Analysis*, Springer International Publishing, 2018.